

Instrument Data Quality Evaluation and Assessment Service - Quality Assurance Framework for Earth Observation (IDEAS-QA4EO)

Final Report

WP-2660: Aerosol and trace gas profiling with synergies between Pandora and MAXDOAS

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Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Retrieval of aerosol and trace gas vertical profiles	3
2.1	MAX-DOAS measurements and slant column retrieval settings	3
2.2	Evaluation of the retrieved dSCDs	6
3	Comparison with the operational MAX-DOAS products	9
3.1	Comparison of the measured dSCDs	9
3.2	Comparison of the simulated dSCDs	10
3.3	Data flagging	11
3.4	Comparison of the retrieved integrated columns	13
3.5	Assessment of the Pandora's performance during the warm and cold period	15
3.6	Validation of the Pandora AODs with collocated CIMEL measurements	17
4	Comparison with the operational Pandora products	19
5	Retrieval of total NO ₂ columns at Thessaloniki	20
5.1	Development of a DOAS-based algorithm	20
5.2	Evaluation of the retrieved NO ₂ columns	23
5.3	Comparison with S5P/TROPOMI observations	26
	Appendix A: Mean averaging kernels	29
	Appendix B: Assessment of flagging algorithms	30
	Appendix C: Comparison with the geometrical approximation	32
	Appendix D: Timeseries of the collocated integrated columns	33
	References	35

1 Introduction

This document is the final report for WP-2660: Aerosol and trace gas profiling with synergies between Pandora and MAXDOAS. The tasks of WP-2660 involve **(i)** the retrieval of tropospheric aerosol and trace gas vertical profiles in Thessaloniki using as input Pandora's spectra and SCDs, and comparison with the operational MAX-DOAS products, **(ii)** comparisons of NO₂ and HCHO vertical profiles and columns from the operational MAX-DOAS profiling algorithms with the Pandora 240 products, **(iii)** validation of the aerosol MAX-DOAS products at Thessaloniki, **(iv)** development of a DOAS-based algorithm for the retrieval of total NO₂ columns using direct sun measurements and determination/optimization of the retrieval settings and **(v)** evaluation of the total NO₂ retrieval algorithm with the Pandora's operational direct sun L2 product.

The document contains a description of the datasets used for the retrieval, evaluation and validation of tropospheric aerosol and trace gas vertical profiles in Thessaloniki using as input L1 spectra (having all calibration procedures and corrections applied) and differential Slant Column Densities (dSCDs) measured by Pandora, as well as on the development and evaluation of a DOAS-based algorithm for the retrieval of total NO₂ columns using direct sun observations at Thessaloniki. In **Sect. 2** the retrieval methodology of the vertical profiles is described, along with intercomparison results of the slant columns measured by Pandora and a collocated research-grade MAX-DOAS instrument (referred to hereafter as "Delta"). In **Sect. 3** the column-integrated products derived using profiling techniques from Pandora are compared with the operational respective MAX-DOAS products, while in **Sect. 4** they are compared with the operational tropospheric Pandora L2 products. In **Sect. 5**, the methodology for the retrieval of total NO₂ columns using direct sun observations of Delta is described and results are presented from the evaluation of the algorithm, the comparison with the total NO₂ Pandora L2 product and the comparison with respective collocated S5P/TROPOMI observations.

2 Retrieval of aerosol and trace gas vertical profiles

2.1 MAX-DOAS measurements and slant column retrieval settings

For the retrieval of tropospheric aerosol and trace gas (NO₂ and HCHO) vertical profiles in Thessaloniki using Pandora's MAX-DOAS observations, two inversion algorithms have been employed, i.e., the Mexican MAXDOAS Fit v2020_04 (MMF; Friedrich et al., 2019), which relies on the Optimal Estimation Method (OEM; Rodgers, 2000) and the Mainz Profile Algorithm v0.98 (MAPA; Beirle et al., 2019), which is based on a parameterization approach. The operational schedule of Pandora in Thessaloniki included measurements at 5 elevation angles (i.e., at 1, 2, 15, 30 and 89°), however, the two profiling algorithms require observations at more than 5 directions (especially close to the horizon) to provide quality-assured vertical profiles. Hence, on 10.11.2023 an extra routine has been included in the operational schedule (namely "E2.rout") with a clear position of the instrument's filter-wheel that allows off-axis measurements at 11 elevation angles (i.e., at 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12, 15, 30°), followed by a

sequential zenith-sky measurement with an integration time of 15 sec per elevation angle. For the species measured in the UV (i.e., HCHO and O₄ at 360 nm) the retrievals were found to be affected by stray light from longer wavelengths and thus, since 15.11.2023 an additional routine (namely “E3.rout”) was included for performing MAX-DOAS observations at the same viewing geometries, using also the same integration times, but with a bandpass U340 filter in order to improve the quality of the measured dSCDs. The Pandora NO₂, HCHO and O₄ dSCDs have been reprocessed locally using the QDOAS software (<https://uv-vis.aeronomie.be/software/QDOAS/>) with the retrieval settings being based on results from the Cabauw Intercomparison of Nitrogen Dioxide Measuring Instruments 2 (CINDI-2) campaign (<http://www.tropomi.eu/data-products/cindi-2/>) (e.g., Kreher et al., 2020), the Quality Assurance for Essential Climate Variables (QA4ECV) project (<http://www.qa4ecv.eu/>), and the Network for Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change (NDACC) protocol for UV–VIS measurements (<http://www.ndaccdemo.org/data/protocols/>). The spectral retrieval settings and the trace gas absorption cross sections that are included in the DOAS analysis are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. DOAS fit settings for NO₂, HCHO, O₄ (VIS), and O₄ (UV). Adapted from Karagkiozidis et al., 2022.

Parameter	Data Source	Trace-gas		
		NO ₂ and O ₄ (VIS)	HCHO	O ₄ (UV)
Spectral range		425 – 490 nm	324.5 – 359 nm	338 – 370 nm
NO ₂ (298 K)	Vandaele et al. (1998), I ₀ -corrected (SCD of 10 ¹⁷ molecules cm ⁻²)	✓	✓	✓
NO ₂ (220 K)	Vandaele et al. (1998), I ₀ -corrected (SCD of 10 ¹⁷ molecules cm ⁻²)	✓		✓
O ₃ (223 K)	Serdyuchenko et al. (2014), I ₀ -corrected (SCD of 10 ²⁰ molecules cm ⁻²)	✓	✓	✓
O ₃ (243 K)	Serdyuchenko et al. (2014), I ₀ -corrected (SCD of 10 ²⁰ molecules cm ⁻²)		✓	✓
O ₄ (293 K)	Thalman and Volkamer (2013)	✓	✓	✓
BrO (223 K)	Fleischmann et al. (2004)		✓	✓
HCHO (297 K)	Meller and Moortgat (2000)		✓	✓
H ₂ O (296 K)	HITEMP, Rothman et al. (2010)	✓		

Ring	Ring spectra calculated by QDOAS according to Chance and Spurr (1997)	✓	✓	✓
Polynomial degree		5	5	5
Intensity offset		Constant	Order 1	Constant
Wavelength Calibration	Based on a high-resolution solar reference spectrum (Chance and Kurucz, 2010)			

The O₄ and trace gas dSCDs retrieved from Pandora have been compared to slant columns measured by a high-quality research-grade MAX-DOAS instrument (“Delta”) operating at Thessaloniki, that performs spectral measurements at the same elevation angles as the Pandora, after finding quasi-simultaneous measurements between the two systems (with a tolerance of ± 5 minutes). Delta is configured to perform elevation scans at 4 azimuth directions, while the routines of Pandora include measurements to a single, fixed, azimuth as illustrated in Figure 1. Hence, the comparisons are conducted only in cases when the two instruments were pointing at the same azimuth direction (i.e., at 220°).

Figure 1. The location of the MAX-DOAS systems (white star) and the azimuth viewing directions of Delta (left) and Pandora (right), represented by the solid red lines. The base map is taken from © Google Maps.

It should be noted that on 06.12.2023 the processing of Pandora measured spectra has been suspended due to hardware issues of the Pandonia Global Network (PGN) servers (<https://www.pandonia-global-network.org/home/about/news-and-events/current-issues/>). However, this issue has been resolved during February 2024 and all missing data have been reprocessed. On 17 May 2024, Delta was uninstalled and packed in order to participate in the CINDI-3 campaign, which took place in Cabauw, the Netherlands, for about a month. The instrument became operational again in Thessaloniki on 26 June 2024. Additionally, during the period 27 June – 22 July 2024, even though Pandora was meant to be operational, both telescopes were found to be blocked by obstacles, probably due to bugs, hence no valid L2 data are available. In this report the evaluation and validation of the Pandora

retrieved products are performed during the period Nov 2023 – Sep 2024, however, for about two months during summer are missing for the aforementioned reasons.

2.2 Evaluation of the retrieved dSCDs

Figure 2 shows a typical example of the DOAS retrieval of NO₂, HCHO and O₄ at two spectral bands using Pandora MAX-DOAS observations by means of the QDOAS software. The trace gas and O₄ dSCDs presented here have been measured on 27 Feb 2024 at 06:23 UTC (SZA ~ 75.7°) at 4° elevation angle and at an azimuth angle of 220°.

Figure 2. A typical example of DOAS retrieval of NO₂, HCHO, O₄ (VIS), and O₄ (UV) dSCDs derived from Pandora. The black lines represent the measured spectra, and red lines are the fitted O₄ and trace gas cross sections.

The DOAS fits for the species measured in the visible range (i.e., NO₂ and O₄ at 477 nm) are of high quality, while for the species in the UV, they are contaminated by spectral noise, especially for HCHO retrievals, where the measured differential optical densities are very low, probably reaching the spectrometer’s detection limit. The corresponding DOAS fits for Delta, measured on the same day at the same viewing directions are presented in Figure 3. The slit function of Delta (~0.85 nm FWHM) is higher than Pandora, thus resulting in a reduced spectral resolution, yet the DOAS fits are of increased quality, which is more evident for O₄ at 360 nm, and especially for HCHO. Figure 4 shows the comparison of the frequency distribution of the DOAS Fit Root Mean Square (RMS) for NO₂, HCHO, O₄ at 477 nm (referred to hereafter as “O₄ VIS”) and O₄ at 360 nm (referred to hereafter as “O₄ UV”), between Pandora and Delta. Data from all elevation angles are included in the analysis and it should also be noted that no cloud filtering has been applied to the data. NO₂ and O₄ VIS are retrieved from the same spectral fitting window, hence their DOAS fit RMS are presented in a single subplot.

Figure 3. Same as Figure 2, but using spectra recorded by the Delta MAX-DOAS instrument.

The corresponding histograms of the DOAS Fit Errors for all trace gases are presented in Figure 5. The DOAS fit RMS frequency distributions for all species are similar and comparable between Delta and Pandora, which is indicative for successful DOAS retrievals, even though the RMS values of Delta are slightly lower. However, the DOAS fit errors of Pandora are significantly higher than those of Delta, especially for the species measured in the UV (HCHO and O₄ UV) which is attributed not only to its comparably lower sensitivity, but it is also related to the lower integration times that have been used for the spectral measurements (15 and 30 sec for Pandora and Delta, respectively), hence resulting to reduced Signal to Noise Ratios (SNR).

Figure 4. Frequency distribution of the DOAS fit RMS for NO₂ and O₄ VIS (upper panel), HCHO (bottom-left panel) and O₄ UV (bottom-right panel).

Figure 5. Frequency distribution of the DOAS fit Errors for NO₂ (upper-left panel), O₄ VIS (upper-right panel), HCHO (bottom-left panel) and O₄ UV (bottom-right panel).

3 Comparison with the operational MAX-DOAS products

3.1 Comparison of the measured dSCDs

Figure 6 shows the intercomparison results of all trace gas dSCDs during the period of study. For the species measured in visible range (i.e., NO₂ and O₄ VIS) a very good agreement is found, indicating generally high-quality DOAS retrievals. The data points are colored by the elevation angle with hotter colors representing dSCDs closer to the horizon. No clear dependence on the elevation angle is observed. The slopes of the regression are 1.020 and 1.039 for NO₂ and O₄ VIS, respectively, while the corresponding correlation coefficients (R) are 0.993. The comparison for the species measured in the UV is poorer, especially for HCHO. In the case of O₄ UV the measured dSCDs are still in reasonable agreement, even though larger scatter is found compared to O₄ VIS, which a slope of 1.030 and R=0.962. For HCHO, large discrepancies are found between the two instruments for all elevation angles, which is mainly attributed to the limited sensitivity in retrieving very low HCHO optical depths. It should be noted that in the reporting period the HCHO levels are generally low in Thessaloniki and the comparison is expected to improve when data become available during summer, when the HCHO levels typically increase (Karagiozidis et al., 2022).

Figure 6. Scatter plots of collocated NO₂ (upper-left panel), O₄ VIS (upper-right panel), HCHO (bottom-left panel) and O₄ UV (bottom-right panel) dSCDs measured by Pandora and Delta.

3.2 Comparison of the simulated dSCDs

The measured dSCDs from both instruments have been used as input to MMF and MAPA for the retrieval of aerosol and trace gas vertical profiles. The retrieval settings are identical for the two systems, as already described in Sect. 2 **Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε..** The NO₂, HCHO and O₄ dSCDs simulated by the forward models of MMF (VLIDORT version 2.7; Spurr, 2006) and MAPA (McArtim; Deutschmann et al., 2011) have been evaluated and the intercomparison results are presented in Figures 7 and 8 for MMF and MAPA, respectively. MAPA allows for the application of a variable O₄ scaling factor (Wagner et al., 2009) to bring measured and simulated O₄ dSCDs into agreement, while no similar option is available in the current version of MMF. Hence, in order to treat the two inversion algorithms equally, no O₄ scaling factor has been applied to MAPA retrievals.

Figure 7. Scatter plots of collocated NO₂ (upper-left panel), O₄ VIS (upper-right panel), HCHO (bottom-left panel) and O₄ UV (bottom-right panel) dSCDs simulated by the forward model of MAPA.

The results are consistent with Figure 6, i.e., they are in very good agreement for NO₂, and O₄ in both spectral bands (especially in the visible range), which is a first good indicator for successful profile retrievals. For HCHO, the simulated slant columns show a poor performance, which is due to the increased noise contained in the DOAS retrievals, as already discussed before. It should also be noted that no negative simulated slant columns are reported by MMF, since, in its current version, MMF operates in logarithmic state vector space. The mean averaging kernels, calculated by MMF during the

whole period of study, are presented in Appendix A (only valid and warning-flagged data were considered) in order to illustrate the sensitivity of Pandora in retrieving the tropospheric vertical profile per altitude layer for each retrieved species.

Figure 8. Same as Figure 7, but for the trace gas dSCDs simulated by the forward model of MAPA.

3.3 Data flagging

MMF and MAPA include an individual quality flagging algorithm that is based on multiple criteria, in order to assess the quality of the retrieved vertical profiles. Each profile retrieval is flagged as either valid, warning or error. The two flagging algorithms are inherently different and thus they treat the input and retrieved data in a different way. For higher-quality products, the suggestion is to use valid data only for MAPA, while the suggestion for MMF is to use both valid and warning-flagged data (Kargkiozidis et al., 2022). Figure 9 shows the fraction of collocated data flagged as valid, warning and error by MMF using Pandora and Delta MAX-DOAS measurements for all the retrieved species. For NO₂, the warning-flagged data are very similar, while Pandora shows a slightly larger fraction of valid data compared to Delta (6% instead of 3%). In the case of HCHO, MMF reports no valid Pandora data for HCHO, and the largest fraction of the data is flagged as warning. However, for Delta, MMF reports 37% valid data, and the error-flagged data are significantly lower than Pandora (5% instead of 15%), which is mainly due to the higher-quality products measured by Delta, especially in the UV, as already discussed in Sect. 2.2 and Sect. 3.1. For O₄ VIS, the reported flagged data are very similar, with almost

no valid data for both instruments and more than 40% being flagged as error, while for O₄ UV, almost all Pandora measurements (95%) as flagged as error. The significantly different flagging between Pandora and Delta confirms the differences in the quality of DOAS retrievals (i.e., the dSCDs), which is the main driver for successful aerosol and trace gas profile retrievals.

Figure 9. Fraction of valid, warning and error flagged data for Delta (left) and Pandora (right) using MMF for NO₂ (a), HCHO (b), O₄ VIS (c) and O₄ UV (d).

Figure 10 presents the same results but using MAPA retrievals. In this case, the NO₂ and O₄ VIS flagged data are very similar for both instruments, with ~25-30% valid data, 40% warnings and 30-35% errors. For HCHO and O₄ UV, a higher fraction of data is flagged as valid by MAPA for Delta retrievals and a much lower fraction as error for reasons that have already been discussed.

Figure 10. Same as Figure 9, but for MAPA retrievals.

3.4 Comparison of the retrieved integrated columns

Figures 11 and 12 present the intercomparison results of column-integrated products (i.e., VCDs for trace gases and AODs for aerosols) using MMF and MAPA, respectively. For MMF comparisons, data flagged as error for any instrument were rejected from the analysis, hence only collocated data, which have been flagged as either valid or warning have been used. For MAPA, only valid data have been accepted for the comparison.

The NO₂ VCDs using MMF are in excellent agreement, with a slope of 1.002 and a Pearson's correlation coefficient (R) of 0.960, which is a good indicator for successful profile retrievals for both instruments. For HCHO, the comparison is poorer with R=0.858, however, as already discussed, the HCHO levels for the reporting period are usually very low, hence the measured signal is weak and there is much noise

in the DOAS retrievals (Sect. 2.2). An additional comparison is required at a time period when the HCHO levels increase, e.g., during summer due to the enhanced biogenic emissions of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs), whose oxidation produces HCHO. For aerosols, even though there is a very good correlation for AODs at 477 nm ($R=0.932$), the AODs measured by Delta are systematically higher than Pandora, for reasons not yet identified, and further assessment and validation is required using data from the collocated CIMEL sun-photometer and Lidar system. The number of available points for AOD at 360 nm is very low, as a result of high fraction of error-flagged (95%) Pandora data (Sect. 3.3), hence the comparison cannot provide statistically robust results.

Figure 11. Intercomparison of column-integrated products, i.e., NO₂ (upper-left panel) and HCHO (bottom-left panel) VCDs and AODs at 477 (upper-right panel) and at 360 nm (lower-right panel) using MMF.

The quality flagging criteria of MAPA are more strict compared to MMF, since only valid-flagged data may be accepted for the comparison. However, the comparisons for NO₂ and AODs in the UV and visible range are significantly improved. For NO₂ a slope of 1.043 and $R=0.985$ are reported, while for AODs at 477 and at 360 nm, the corresponding slopes of the regression analysis are $S=0.947$ and $S=0.923$, respectively, with correlation coefficients $R=0.981$ and $R=0.908$, respectively. The HCHO VCDs are still not in good agreement, for reasons that have already been discussed.

Figure 12. Same as Figure 11 but using MAPA retrievals.

3.5 Assessment of the Pandora's performance during the warm and cold period

In this section we investigate the Pandora's performance in retrieving trace gas and O₄ dSCDs during the warm and cold period, which typically correspond to different air pollution conditions over Thessaloniki. As previously seen (see Figure 6), poor agreement is found in the measured HCHO dSCDs between Delta and Pandora. Figure 13 shows two examples of HCHO DOAS fits, during winter and summer, respectively. The trace gas fits presented here are based on spectra measured at 4° elevation angle at a solar zenith angle of ~60° on 17 Dec 2023 and on 29 July 2024 (both being clear-sky days) for the cold and warm periods, respectively. The poorer quality of the HCHO retrieval during the cold period is evident and can be explained by the increased spectral noise in the UV in addition to the low differential optical densities, reaching the spectrometer's detection limit.

Figure 13. Two examples of HCHO DOAS retrievals derived from Pandora during the cold (left) and warm (right) period. The black lines represent the measured spectra and the red lines are the fitted HCHO cross sections.

Figure 14 shows the intercomparison results of NO₂, HCHO and O₄ in the UV and visible ranges during the whole period of study (from Nov 2023 to Sep 2024). For the species measured in the visible region, the measured dSCDs are in very good agreement for both periods, indicating generally high-quality data for both instruments. For NO₂ retrievals, the slopes of the regression are 1.026 and 1.005, with correlation coefficients R=0.994 and R=0.983, for the cold and warm periods, respectively. For O₄ (VIS), the corresponding slopes are 1.040 and 1.047, while the correlation coefficients are R=0.994 and R=0.990, respectively. The comparison for the species measured in the UV is generally poorer for reasons already discussed. However, especially for HCHO, the comparison is greatly improved during the warm period, when the HCHO concentrations are significantly higher, with the correlation coefficient increasing from R=0.532 to R=0.853. Despite the relatively better agreement during summer, larger scatter is found compared to the species measured in the VIS, which can be explained by the increased spectral noise in the UV (especially for Pandora). For O₄ in the UV, even though the comparison is less good than for O₄ VIS, the two instruments are yet in very reasonable agreement with slopes of 1.023 and 1.043 and correlation coefficients of R=0.966 and R=0.944, for the cold and warm periods, respectively. It should also be noted that no cloud filtering has been applied to the data, and the larger scatter that is found during winter can be partially explained by the more frequent cloudy conditions, that can have a strong effect on the O₄ retrievals.

Figure 14. Intercomparison of NO₂ (upper-left panel), O₄ VIS (upper-right panel), HCHO (bottom-left panel) and O₄ UV (bottom-right panel) dSCDs between Pandora and Delta for the warm and cold period.

3.6 Validation of the Pandora AODs with collocated CIMEL measurements

The AODs at 477 and 360 nm retrieved by Pandora are compared with the respective AODs measured by the co-located CIMEL sun photometer (shown in Figure 15). Quasi-simultaneous (within ± 15 min) measurements were found, while the AODs at 477 and 360 nm were calculated using the Ångström exponent between 380 and 500 nm and the AOD at these wavelengths derived by the CIMEL sun photometer. A comparison for the AOD retrievals in the UV using MMF is not presented here, since only a small fraction of the data is flagged as valid in this case (see Figure 9), leading to a very small number of available collocations and hence to not statistically robust conclusions.

Figure 15. Comparison of the AODs retrieved by Pandora with collocated CIMEL observations. The upper panel corresponds to AOD retrievals using MMF in the VIS (477 nm), the bottom-left panel using MAPA in the VIS (477 nm) and the bottom-right panel using MAPA in the UV (360 nm).

The AODs derived from Pandora, in both the UV and the VIS range, are, generally, underestimated compared to the AODs measured by the CIMEL sun photometer. This finding is consistent with other studies (e.g., Clmer et al., 2010; Bsch et al., 2018; Davis et al., 2020; Tirpitz et al., 2021). However, it should be noted that the AODs derived by Pandora and the reference instrument may not always refer to the same physical quantity. The CIMEL sun photometer uses direct-sun observations to retrieve the total column amount of the aerosol extinction, while the sensitivity of the MAX-DOAS technique decreases rapidly with altitude (Frie et al., 2016; 2019), and the derived AOD corresponds mainly to the lowermost tropospheric aerosol (partial AOD). Additionally, the vertical profiles retrieved by OEM-based algorithms are biased towards the a priori profile at higher altitudes, leading to deviations from the true profile, meaning that aerosol layers above ≈ 2 km cannot be reliably retrieved. Discrepancies in the AODs between the instruments are expected, usually when aerosols are present at altitudes greater than 2 km, contributing to the total AOD, but not detected by Pandora. The performance of MAPA using Pandora data is slightly better compared to MMF, even though the correlation coefficients are comparable (of about 0.65), the slopes of the regression using MAPA are significantly higher (~ 0.67) than MMF (0.46).

4 Comparison with the operational Pandora products

In this section, the comparisons are presented of the tropospheric NO₂ and HCHO VCDs that are retrieved using profiling techniques (i.e., using MMF and MAPA) with the operational Pandora L2 products. The L2 products contain a data quality flag for the retrievals. For these comparisons, the flagging scheme that is applied includes data flagged as valid or warning by MMF (only valid-flagged data for MAPA retrievals) and additionally only high- or medium-quality data that are reported in the L2 products. For NO₂ the operational product shows a good correlation with MMF and MAPA retrievals ($R=0.931$ and $R=0.845$, respectively), however the reported columns are negatively biased in both cases (reported slopes of 0.784 and 0.641, respectively). An assessment of different flagging schemes applied to the data is presented in Appendix B, where the same comparisons are presented, but by filtering the data with the flagging algorithms of Pandora, MAPA and MMF. The HCHO columns are not in good agreement and thus further investigation is required. In Appendix C, NO₂ and HCHO VCDs obtained from the integration of the vertical profiles retrieved by MMF and MAPA are compared with those derived by geometrical approximation (Hönninger and Platt, 2002). The timeseries of the collocated tropospheric integrated columns are presented in Appendix D. The reasons for the gap that is found in the timeseries during summer 2024 are discussed in Sect. 2.1.

Figure 16. Comparison of NO₂ (left) and HCHO (right) tropospheric VCDs between the operational Pandora L2 product and MMF retrievals.

Figure 17. Same as Figure 16, but for MAPA retrievals.

5 Retrieval of total NO₂ columns at Thessaloniki

Within the frame of IDEAS-QA4EO, a DOAS-based algorithm was developed for the retrieval of total NO₂ columns at Thessaloniki using direct sun observations performed by Delta. In the following subsections, the theoretical background of the algorithm is described, along with results from the evaluation of the retrieved columns and the comparison with the operational Pandora L2 product, as well as comparison with collocated total NO₂ data measured by the TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) on board Sentinel-5 Precursor (S5P) (Veefkind et al., 2012).

5.1 Development of a DOAS-based algorithm

The Direct Sun DOAS (DS-DOAS) technique offers several advantages over DOAS analysis employing scattered radiation spectra. The VCDs are calculated by division with the Air Mass Factor (AMF), which closely approximates the secant of the solar zenith angle, eliminating the necessity for radiative transfer calculations and rendering it unaffected by the Ring effect. Additionally, DS-DOAS does not require prior knowledge of the NO₂ vertical profile, ground reflectivity, or assumptions of horizontal homogeneity, as opposed to traditional methods (Cede et al., 2006; Herman et al., 2009). However, it exhibits equal sensitivity to both tropospheric and stratospheric NO₂ components, with the latter being at least 10 times less abundant. In the DOAS analysis, the direct irradiance spectra are compared to a reference spectrum to derive the differential slant column density (dSCD) of NO₂ along the path of the solar beam. The reference spectrum is usually measured on a clear day around local noon to achieve the weakest attenuation of radiation. If SCD_z is the slant column density of NO₂ for a spectrum recorded at a solar zenith angle (SZA_z) and SCD_{ref} is the slant column density of the reference spectrum then the differential slant column density can be calculated as:

$$dSCD = SCD - SCD_{ref} \quad (1)$$

A spectrum measured on 24/06/2023 with SZA of 17.22° is used as reference spectrum in the DOAS analysis. This particular day was characterized by very clear-sky conditions, along with relatively low AOD and tropospheric NO₂ levels. The analysis was conducted following two different methods. The first method includes NO₂ absorption cross sections at two different temperatures (i.e., at 294 and 220 K, respectively) representative for the tropospheric and stratospheric absorption of NO₂, respectively (two-T method). The second method uses the NO₂ absorption cross section at 254.5 K, which was derived from the two temperatures of the first method by interpolation (one-T method). The settings that have been used for the retrieval of NO₂ dSCDs for both methods (i.e., the window of the spectral fitting, the cross sections of other trace gases absorbing in the same spectral region, the degree of polynomials used to remove the broad-band features, etc.), are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. DOAS fit settings for the retrieval of NO₂ dSCDs using the One-T and Two-T methods.

Parameter	Data source	Two-T Method		One-T Method
		NO ₂ [220 K]	NO ₂ [294 K]	NO ₂ [254.5 K]
Spectral range		400 – 470 nm	400 – 470 nm	400 – 470 nm
NO ₂ (220 K)	Vandaele et al. (1998), I ₀ -corrected (SCD in 10 ¹⁷ molec. cm ⁻²)	✓		
NO ₂ (294 K)	Vandaele et al. (1998), I ₀ -corrected (SCD in 10 ¹⁷ molec. cm ⁻²)		✓	
NO ₂ (254.5 K)	Vandaele et al. (1998), I ₀ -corrected (SCD in 10 ¹⁷ molec. cm ⁻²)			✓
O ₃ (223 K)	Serdyuchenko et al. (2014), I ₀ -corrected (SCD in 10 ²⁰ molec. cm ⁻²)	✓	✓	✓
O ₄ (262 K)	Thalman and Volkamer (2013)	✓	✓	✓
H ₂ O (293 K)	HITEMP, Rothman et al. (2010)	✓	✓	✓
OIO (298 K)	Spietz et al. (2005)	✓	✓	✓
I ₂ (295 K)	Saiz- Lopez and Plane (2004)	✓	✓	✓
Polynomial degree		4	4	4
Intensity offset		Constant	Constant	Constant
Wavelength calibration	Based on a high-resolution solar reference spectrum (Chance and Kurudz, 2010)			

For the two-T method, the total NO₂ dSCDs can be represented by two components, each being sensitive to the absorption of NO₂ in the troposphere and the stratosphere, respectively. It is further assumed that the variability of the NO₂ total column is mainly governed by the variability of tropospheric

NO_2 , hence the stratospheric NO_2 component can be substituted by its climatological values. The $dSCD$ is then given by:

$$dSCD = dSCD_T \times \left[\frac{(1 - q_{CLIM} \times AMF_S)}{dSCD_S} \right] + AMF_S \times q_{CLIM} \quad (2)$$

where $dSCD_T$ and $dSCD_S$ are the differential slant columns of NO_2 derived by the DOAS fitting using the NO_2 cross sections for the tropospheric and stratospheric temperatures, respectively, AMF_S is the air mass factor calculated for the absorption of NO_2 occurring in the stratosphere, and q_{CLIM} represents the climatological value of the stratospheric NO_2 column for the location, season, and time of each measurement. A more detailed description on the derivation of (2) can be found in Cede et al., (2019). The AMF is calculated from the equation (3), which takes into account the actual path or radiation traversing the stratosphere, which is different from the path in other atmospheric layers due to the curvature of the Earth:

$$AMF = \sec(\arcsin(r / (r + h_{eff}) \sin z_\alpha)) \quad (3)$$

where r is the Earth's radius at the measurement location (~ 6370 km for 40° N), z_α is the apparent solar zenith angle (i.e., the true SZA corrected for refraction), and $h_{eff} = 25$ km is the assumed effective height of the stratospheric NO_2 layer. For the tropospheric AMF_S , h_{eff} is assumed at 2 km and at 12.5 km for AMF_S of the total column. The climatological values of stratospheric NO_2 , q_{CLIM} , were calculated by means of a photochemical model, which takes into account the stratospheric species that are important for stratospheric chemistry.

Figure 18. An example of stratospheric NO_2 concentration during a winter and a summer day according to the stratospheric NO_2 climatology.

The NO_2 column represents the total vertical accumulation of NO_2 concentration. The simulation portrays the amount of stratospheric NO_2 present in an uncontaminated atmosphere devoid of

tropospheric emissions. Figure 18 shows two examples of the diurnal variability of the stratospheric NO₂ for Thessaloniki during a winter and a summer day.

According to equation (1), to derive the NO₂ SCD from the dSCD, the SCD_{ref} is needed, and it is estimated by applying the Bootstrap Estimation (BE) method suggested by Herman et al., (2009). This method can be applied when a large number of dSCD data is available measured at an adequate range of AMFs. It is assumed that for each AMF the lowest dSCD data are very close to the minimum value and that this value can be estimated statistically. In Figure 19a the dSCDs measured at Thessaloniki by applying the two-T method are plotted as a function of AMF. This AMF is derived from equation (3) using h_{eff} = 12.5 km, that corresponds to the radiation path for the entire atmosphere. After grouping the data into bins of AMF (in steps of 0.25), the average dSCD of the 5th percentile of the group is calculated and is assumed to correspond to the minimum dSCD for the respective AMF. The AMF corresponding to each bin is the average AMF of all points forming the 5th percentile. The constant term of the linear regression between the dSCD minima and AMF provides the required SCD_{ref}, which in this case is calculated at 7.6074 Pmolec. cm⁻² (Figure 19a). Finally, rewriting equation (1), the vertical column density of NO₂ can be calculated from (4):

$$VCD = dSCD/AMF_z + SCD_{ref} \quad (4)$$

In the one-T method, the dSCD is calculated directly by the QDOAS analysis using the NO₂ cross section at a single temperature (254.5 K). This simpler method does not distinguish the absorption by NO₂ in the troposphere and stratosphere. The VCD is derived directly from equation (4) with the AMF calculated by equation (3) for h_{eff} = 12.5 km, while the SCD_{ref} is estimated by the BE method, as in the one-T method. The corresponding analysis is depicted in Figure 19b, resulting in SCD_{REF} = 6.2638 Pmolec/cm².

Figure 19. Estimation of the NO₂ SCD of the reference spectrum that was used in the DOAS analysis for the two retrieval methods: two-T (A) and one-T (B). Small gray symbols represent the dSCDs and large green symbols the mean of the lowest 5% of the data in each AMF bin. The red line is the linear regression between the mean of the lowest 5% dSCDs and the corresponding AMFs.

5.2 Evaluation of the retrieved NO₂ columns

Here, the retrieved NO₂ columns are evaluated and the comparison of the two different methods for retrieving NO₂ VCDs is presented. The NO₂ VCDs derived from the Delta system by applying the two retrieval methods are filtered according to the DOAS fitting RMS error. Figure 20 shows the frequency distribution of the DOAS fitting RMS error for the two retrieval methods.

Figure 20. Frequency distribution of the DOAS fit RMS for the two NO₂ retrieval methods applied on Delta data using three different temperatures. The vertical dashed line marks the threshold of 2×10^{-3} that was used to filter the measurements.

Most of the data (95% for both methods) have RMS values below a set threshold (i.e., 2×10^{-3}) (Kumar et al., 2020), indicative of successful DOAS retrievals. The total NO₂ VCDs derived from Delta by the two methods are compared in Figure 21. Despite the excellent correlation of 0.999, the scatter shows that the one-T method underestimates the total VCD by up to 15% compared to the two-T method, with the difference increasing with VCD.

Figure 21. Comparison of total NO₂ VCDs derived from Delta by the one-T and two-T retrieval methods. The red line is the linear fit and the dashed line is the $y = x$.

In order to compare the two fitting methods, we calculated the ratio of the total NO₂ VCDs derived by the one-T and the two-T methods. Moreover, we calculated the fraction of the tropospheric to the total NO₂ VCD, both derived by the two-T method. Figure 22A shows the time series of the NO₂ ratio

of the two methods, colored by the tropospheric fraction. The ~2-month gap during summer 2022 is due to instrument maintenance.

Figure 22. A) Time series of the ratio of NO₂ VCD derived by the one-T and the two-T methods. The data points are colored according to the fraction of the total NO₂ column derived for the 294 K (tropospheric) temperature. B) Mean diurnal variability of the ratio (one-T/two-T) during winter (December, January, February) and summer (June, July, August). The error bars represent the 1 σ variability of each hourly mean during each season.

We observe that the one-T method underestimates the total VCDs of NO₂ when the tropospheric fraction is high. This is more evident in the cold period of the year when the emissions of tropospheric NO₂ are higher and dominant in the total column throughout the day. In contrast, during the warm period of the year the tropospheric columns are relatively high only in the morning hours since NO₂ is quickly photolyzed as solar radiation increases. This large diurnal variability is evident in Figure 22A, resulting also in large variability of the tropospheric NO₂ fraction, with low values corresponding to periods in the day with the total column of NO₂ practically composed only by the stratospheric component. In these cases, the one-T method gives comparable results with the two-T method.

Figure 22B shows the mean diurnal variability of hourly mean total NO₂ VCD derived by the one-T and two-T methods during winter and summer. The average difference between the two methods is slightly smaller in the summer (closer to unity) compared to winter. It also decreases from morning to evening, consistently with the diurnal variability of the ratio shown in Figure 22A. From Figure 22B it is also obvious that during winter, when tropospheric NO₂ concentrations are higher (Pinardi et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2013), the one-T method underestimates the Total NO₂ VCD. The contribution of stratospheric NO₂ to the total column in winter is minimal compared to the tropospheric component, as shown in Figure 18. The conclusion drawn from the two figures is that when one component (tropospheric or stratospheric) prevails over the other, the two-T method estimates better the total NO₂ VCD. From the comparison of the two methods, we conclude that the two-T method is more appropriate to represent the variability of the total NO₂ column during the year, assuming of course that the climatology of stratospheric NO₂ represents adequately the true variability.

The NO₂ VCDs retrieved by Delta with the two-T method are compared with the operational total NO₂ L2 product of Pandora, using collocated measurements with a tolerance of ±5 min. The Pandora data are associated with a quality flag of the retrievals; in this case, only high- and medium-quality data have been used in the comparison. Figure 23 shows the histogram of the percentage differences between the total NO₂ VCD of Pandora and Delta and the corresponding scatter plot. Half of the data agree to within ±6.5%, implying a good agreement of the two systems.

Figure 23. Left: the histogram of percentage differences between the total NO₂ VCD of Pandora and Delta ($VCD_{\text{Pandora}} - VCD_{\text{Delta}}$). Right: The corresponding scatter plot of the data. The red line is the linear regression, and the dashed black line is the $y=x$ line.

The agreement was assessed by the mean and median biases (-1.7% and -1.4% respectively) which capture the average and the median of the deviations between the two datasets. Both are slightly negative suggesting that Pandora underestimates the total NO₂ VCD, on average by about 1.5%. The scatter plot indicates a good agreement between the two systems with a correlation coefficient $R=0.973$, albeit with a significant spread which can be as high as 40%. Despite the positive slope of the regression, most of the data points are accumulated below ~20 Pmolec. cm⁻² and have on average negative differences, consistent with the data of the histogram. Comparisons for individual months (not shown here) reveal that this level of agreement applies to all months. The range of the measured VCDs (exceeding 35 Pmolec. cm⁻²) confirms that Thessaloniki is characterized by high amounts of NO₂, which are dominated by the NO₂ in the troposphere (Karagkiozidis et al., 2022; Karagkiozidis et al., 2023), since the stratospheric VCD is only 1-4 Pmolec. cm⁻² (see Figure 18).

5.3 Comparison with S5P/TROPOMI observations

After establishing the method to derive the total NO₂ VCD from Delta we proceeded on a comparison of these retrievals with collocated TROPOMI total NO₂ observations. For each satellite's overpass, the closest pixel to Thessaloniki's station was chosen, is the distance from the center of the pixel is equal to or shorter than 3 km, to ensure that the TROPOMI pixel contains or is very close to the location of Delta. In this comparative analysis only satellite observations with the highest accuracy ($qa = 100$) were allowed. The collocated measurements of TROPOMI and Delta were chosen with a time tolerance of ±30 minutes and are compared in the scatter plot of Figure 24.

Figure 14. Comparison of total NO₂ VCDs of TROPOMI and Delta recorded within 30 min. The red symbols represent single measurements, while the solid black symbols the monthly mean data. The red and black lines are the linear fits of the single data (1) and the monthly mean data (2), respectively, while the dashed line is the $y=x$ line.

Overall, a good agreement is achieved with respect to the variability of both the individual data points and their monthly means, with correlation coefficients of 0.82 and 0.92, respectively. However, in both datasets the slopes of 0.40 and 0.47 are by far different from the ideal case of unity, indicating an underestimation of TROPOMI. For the single data, the mean percentage difference of TROPOMI from Delta is -17.7% , while the absolute differences have a mean of -2.14 ± 2.75 Pmolec. cm^{-2} (mean bias) and a median of -1.48 ± 2.75 Pmolec. cm^{-2} (median bias). Not many studies have reported comparisons of total NO₂ VCDs either between ground-based or between satellite instruments. Such behavior (slope of 0.4) has been reported by Pettinari et al., 2022, using data from a station in southern Italy near Lecce with environmental characteristics similar to those of Thessaloniki. According to Lambert et al., 2024 the median percentage difference of TROPOMI from 70 Pandora stations was $-7.4 \pm 15\%$ (-0.6 ± 1.6 Pmolec. cm^{-2}) and a Pearson's correlation coefficient of 0.7. When stations were categorized by air pollution levels, the median of the mean percentage difference of 28 stations with NO₂ VCDs below 6 Pmolec. cm^{-2} was $+5.8\%$ (clean stations), while for the remaining 42 (polluted) stations the median bias was -17.7% . Evidently, the agreement is better for low NO₂ VCDs and worsens with increasing VCDs, pointing to the well-known difficulty of TROPOMI and other satellite instruments to detect the entire NO₂ column over areas with intense sources of NO₂ near the ground. By comparing Thessaloniki's Pandora measurements with TROPOMI, the results are similar as expected. The correlation coefficient of individual data is 0.81 with a mean bias (-2.63 ± 3.06 Pmolec. cm^{-2}) and mean percentage difference of -20% , slightly higher than the one reported for the 70 PGN stations in Lambert et al., 2024, but similar to the differences between TROPOMI and Delta. The relatively large dispersion of the differences arises mainly from the different geometries of the measurements in conjunction with the horizontal and vertical spatial variability of NO₂ near the surface. Note that the ground-based systems sense the NO₂ absorption along the path of the direct solar radiation (which also varies during the day and seasonally), while TROPOMI detects the upwelling scattered radiance.

Appendix A: Mean averaging kernels

Figure A1. The mean averaging kernels reported by MMF for different altitudes of each species using Pandora measurements. Hotter colors correspond to altitudes closer to the ground.

Appendix B: Assessment of flagging algorithms

Figure B1. Comparison of NO₂ (left) and HCHO (right) tropospheric VCDs between the operational Pandora L2 product and MMF retrievals. The data are flagged by the flagging algorithm of MMF.

Figure B2. Same as Figure B1, but for MAPA retrievals, using its own flagging algorithm.

Figure B3. Comparison of NO₂ (left) and HCHO (right) tropospheric VCDs between the operational Pandora L2 product and MMF retrievals. The data are flagged by the flagging algorithm of Pandora.

Figure B4. Same as Figure B3, but for MAPA retrievals.

Appendix C: Comparison with the geometrical approximation

Figure C1. Comparison of the VCDs from the operational Pandora L2 product (red) and the VCDs retrieved using MMF (blue) with the VCDs calculated using the geometrical approximation (from 15° elevation angle). Data that are flagged as valid or warning by MMF and as high- or medium-quality from the Pandora flagging algorithm have been used.

Figure C2. Same as Figure C1, but for MAPA retrievals. Data that are flagged as valid by MAPA and as high- or medium-quality from the Pandora flagging algorithm have been used.

Appendix D: Timeseries of the collocated integrated columns

Figure D1. Timeseries of collocated integrated columns between Pandora and Delta using MMF. Data that are flagged as either valid or warning by MMF for both instruments have been used.

Figure D2. Same as Figure D1, but using MAPA retrievals. Data that are flagged as valid by MAPA for both instruments have been used.

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